

PL4XGL: A Programming Language Approach to Explainable Graph Learning

Supplementary Material

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A IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS OF OUR ALGORITHM

This section presents the detailed implementation of our learning algorithm described in Section 5 of our paper.

Specializing Intervals in Top-Down Algorithm. Our implementation of *SpecializeItv* in Figure 6 narrows an interval by dividing it at median values follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SpecializeItv}(\langle [a_1, b_1], [a_2, b_2], \dots [a_k, b_k] \rangle) = \\ \{ \langle [a'_1, b'_1], [a'_2, b'_2], \dots, [a'_k, b'_k] \rangle \mid j \in [1, k], \forall i \neq j. a'_j = m, b'_j = b_j, a'_i = a_i, b'_i = b_i \} \cup \\ \{ \langle [a'_1, b'_1], [a'_2, b'_2], \dots, [a'_k, b'_k] \rangle \mid j \in [1, k], \forall i \neq j. a'_j = a_j, b'_j = m, a'_i = a_i, b'_i = b_i \} \end{aligned}$$

where m is a median feature value within the interval $[a_j, b_j]$ for the training set (e.g., the number of training nodes with the j^{th} feature value in the interval $[a_j, m]$ is equal to the number of training nodes with the j^{th} feature value in $[m, b_j]$).

Generalizing Intervals in Bottom-Up Algorithm. Our implementation of *GeneralizeItv* in Figure 7 widens an interval by replacing its lower or upper bound with $-\infty$ or ∞ , respectively, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GeneralizeItv}(\langle [a_1, b_1], [a_2, b_2], \dots [a_k, b_k] \rangle) = \\ \{ \langle [a'_1, b'_1], [a'_2, b'_2], \dots [a'_k, b'_k] \rangle \mid j \in [1, k], \forall i \neq j. a'_j = -\infty, b'_j = b_j, a'_i = a_i, b'_i = b_i \} \cup \\ \{ \langle [a'_1, b'_1], [a'_2, b'_2], \dots [a'_k, b'_k] \rangle \mid j \in [1, k], \forall i \neq j. a'_j = a_j, b'_j = \infty, a'_i = a_i, b'_i = b_i \}. \end{aligned}$$

Implementation of Initialize in Bottom-Up Algorithm. In node classification tasks, a graph component c is a pair of a featured graph $G = (V, E, F_V, F_E) \in \mathbb{G}$ and a node $v' \in V$ (i.e., $c = (G, v')$). Suppose $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_p\}$ and $E = \{(v_{i_1}, v_{j_1}), (v_{i_2}, v_{j_2}), \dots, (v_{i_q}, v_{j_q})\}$. Then, *Initialize*(c) returns the following GDL program P using a $\text{map} : V \rightarrow \mathbb{X}$, which maps each node in V into a distinct variable in \mathbb{X} :

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node map(v1) < [fv1,1G, fv1,1G], [fv1,2G, fv1,2G], ..., [fv1,nG, fv1,nG] >
node map(v2) < [fv2,1G, fv2,1G], [fv2,2G, fv2,2G], ..., [fv2,nG, fv2,nG] >
...
node map(vp) < [fvp,1G, fvp,1G], [fvp,2G, fvp,2G], ..., [fvp,nG, fvp,nG] >
edge (map(vi1), map(vj1)) < [f(vi1,vj1),1G, f(vi1,vj1),1G], ..., [f(vi1,vj1),mG, f(vi1,vj1),mG] >
edge (map(vi2), map(vj2)) < [f(vi2,vj2),1G, f(vi2,vj2),1G], ..., [f(vi2,vj2),mG, f(vi2,vj2),mG] >
...
edge (map(viq), map(vjq)) < [f(viq,vjq),1G, f(viq,vjq),1G], ..., [f(viq,vjq),mG, f(viq,vjq),mG] >
target node map(v')
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where $f_{v,r}^G$ presents the r^{th} value of the feature vector \mathbf{f}_v^G . That is, each node or edge with feature values becomes a node or edge variable with specific constraints, respectively. In edge classification

tasks, where $c = (G, (v', v''))$ the last line of the program becomes **target edge** ($map(v')$, $map(v'')$). In graph classification tasks ($c = G$), the last line of the program becomes **target graph**. For example, $c = (G_1, v_1)$ of the following graph

can be transformed into the following GDL program P (i.e., $Initialize(c) = P$):

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node v1 <[1.2, 1.2]>
node v2 <[0.2, 0.2]>
node v3 <[0.4, 0.4]>
node v4 <[0.8, 0.8]>
edge (v2, v1)
edge (v2, v4)
edge (v3, v4)
target node v1

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where $map(v_1) = v1$, $map(v_2) = v2$, $map(v_3) = v3$, and $map(v_4) = v4$.

$CreateInitial(c)$ returns a specific enough GDL program P that satisfies $\forall P' \sqsubset P.c \notin \llbracket P' \rrbracket$. This is because a more specialized program P' necessarily includes additional node or edge variables. Then, it becomes impossible to find a valuation η satisfying $(G_1, \eta) \in \llbracket P' \rrbracket$ as P' contains more node or edge variables than those nodes or edges in G_1 ; it is unable to find a valuation η that maps each variable to a distinct node or edge in G .

B PROOF OF THEOREM 6.1

Theorem 6.1 of our paper claims that if PL4XGL (\mathcal{M}) classifies a graph G into a label i and provides a GDL program $P = \bar{\delta}$ **target graph** as an explanation, which implies PL4XGL (\mathcal{M}) classified the graph with a triple $(i, P, \psi) \in \mathcal{M}$, PL4XGL will classify all the subgraphs in $\{G|_\eta \mid (G, \eta) \in \llbracket \bar{\delta} \rrbracket\}$ into the same label i . We will prove the theorem by demonstrating that assuming the theorem to be invalid leads to a contradiction.

PROOF. Given that the model \mathcal{M} classifies the graph G into label i with the triple $(i, P, \psi) \in \mathcal{M}$, we have:

$$\forall (k, P', \psi') \in \{(k, P', \psi') \in \mathcal{M} \mid G \in \llbracket P' \rrbracket\}. \psi' \leq \psi. \quad (1)$$

Suppose PL4XGL classifies a subgraph $G' \in \{G|_\eta \mid (G, \eta) \in \llbracket \bar{\delta} \rrbracket\}$ into a different label j using another triple $(j, P'', \psi'') \in \mathcal{M}$. Then, we have:

$$\forall (k, P', \psi') \in \{(k, P', \psi') \in \mathcal{M} \mid G' \in \llbracket P' \rrbracket\}. \psi' \leq \psi''. \quad (2)$$

We have (2) and $G' \in \llbracket \bar{\delta} \rrbracket$. Then, we have :

$$G' \in \llbracket P \rrbracket, \psi \leq \psi''. \quad (3)$$

G' is a subgraph of G , and we have (1). Then, we have:

$$G \in \llbracket P'' \rrbracket, \psi \geq \psi''. \quad (4)$$

From (3) and (4), we have

$$\{G, G'\} \subseteq \llbracket P \rrbracket, \{G, G'\} \subseteq \llbracket P'' \rrbracket, \psi = \psi''. \quad (5)$$

From (1), (2) and (5), we have that the two triples (i, P, ψ) and (j, P'', ψ'') describe the both original graph G and the subgraph G' , and they have the same (best) score. We also have that PL4XGL classifies the graph G into the label i . This implies that PL4XGL classifies a graph into the label i if two

triples (i, P''', ψ''') and (j, P''''', ψ''''') , describing the graph, have the same (best) score. However, this contradicts the assumption that PL4XGL classifies the subgraph G' into the label j . \square

PL4XGL also provides inherently model-faithful explanations for node classification; the following theorem holds.

THEOREM B.1. *If PL4XGL classifies a node v_1 in G into a label i and provides a GDL program $P = \bar{\delta}$ target node x , PL4XGL classifies the node v_1 in all the subgraphs in $\{G|_\eta \mid (G, \eta) \in \llbracket \bar{\delta} \rrbracket\}$.*

PROOF. Given that PL4XGL (\mathcal{M}) classifies the node v_1 using the program P , which implies there is a triple $(i, P, \psi) \in \mathcal{M}$ that leads the classification, we have:

$$\forall (k, P', \psi') \in \{(k, P', \psi') \in \mathcal{M} \mid v_1 \in \llbracket P' \rrbracket\}. \psi' \leq \psi. \quad (6)$$

Suppose that PL4XGL classifies a node v'_1 in a subgraph G' , which corresponds to v_1 in the graph G , into a different label j using another triple $(j, P'', \psi'') \in \mathcal{M}$. This implies the following:

$$\forall (k, P', \psi') \in \{(k, P', \psi') \in \mathcal{M} \mid v'_1 \in \llbracket P' \rrbracket\}. \psi' \leq \psi''. \quad (7)$$

G' is described by δ and we have (7). Then, we have

$$v_1 \in \llbracket P \rrbracket, \psi \leq \psi''. \quad (8)$$

G' is a subgraph of G , v'_1 in G' corresponds to v_1 in G , and we have (6). Then, we have:

$$v'_1 \in \llbracket P'' \rrbracket, \psi \geq \psi''. \quad (9)$$

From (8) and (9), we have

$$\{v_1, v'_1\} \in \llbracket P \rrbracket, \{v_1, v'_1\} \in \llbracket P'' \rrbracket, \psi = \psi''. \quad (10)$$

From (6), (7) and (10), we have that the two triples (i, P, ψ) and (j, P'', ψ'') describe the nodes v_1 in the original graph G and v'_1 in the subgraph G' , respectively, and they have the same (best) score. We also have that PL4XGL classifies the node v_1 in the graph G into label i . This implies that PL4XGL classifies a node into the label i when two triples (i, P''', ψ''') and (j, P''''', ψ''''') , describing the node, have the same (best) score. This contradicts the assumption that PL4XGL classified the node v'_1 in the subgraph G' into the label j . \square

C DETAILS OF TRAINING GNNS

To train the GNNs, we used the Adam optimizer [Kingma and Ba 2014] with ℓ_2 -regularization. When optimizing hyperparameters, we employed the search space used in previous works [Park et al. 2022; Yuan et al. 2021]. For the three graph classification datasets and synthetic datasets, we employed the hyperparameters used by Yuan et al. [2021] which evaluates GNNs for the datasets. For the *web page* datasets, we used 500 epochs, learning rate in $\{0.01, 0.005\}$, weight decay in $\{1e-3, 5e-4, 5e-5\}$, hidden dimension in $\{32, 64\}$, and 0.5 dropout rate, used in Park et al. [2022]. We used the artifact of Liu et al. [2021] that provides GCN, GAT, GIN. We additionally implemented CHEBYNET, JKNET, and GRAPHSAGE on it. We used the artifact of Park et al. [2022] for evaluating DGCN. We chose the hyperparameters that maximized the performance on the validation sets.

We observed that, for the MUTAG and BBBP datasets, the reported accuracies of GIN (100.0 for MUTAG) and GCN (86.6 for BBBP) in the existing work [Yuan et al. 2021] were difficult to replicate in our evaluation. This discrepancy is perhaps due to the randomness of GNNs. We conducted multiple experiments with GIN and GCN, but the majority of our learning outcomes resulted in lower classification accuracy compared to the previously reported accuracy. However, we note that even their accuracies reported in the existing work [Yuan et al. 2021] are either equal or lower than those achieved by PL4XGL in Table 3 of our paper.

PL4XGL		SUBGRAPHX	
	$Generality_{P_i}$ 0.77 (96/124)		$Generality_{G'_i}$ 0.38 (48/125)
	$Precision_{P_i}$ 1.0 (96/96)		$Precision_{G'_i}$ 1.0 (48/48)

Fig. 1. How *Generality* and *Precision* are evaluated for PL4XGL and SUBGRAPHX

D COMPARING GENERALITY OF EXPLANATIONS

In this section, we compare the generality of those explanations produced from PL4XGL and SUBGRAPHX. To compare the generality, we introduce a new metric, called *Generality*. The rationale behind *Generality* is that an effective explanation should be general, meaning that a single explanation can explain multiple classification results of the model.

$$Generality = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\# \text{ of predictions classified into } y_i \text{ and explained by } \mathcal{E}_i}{\# \text{ of predictions classified into } y_i} \quad (\text{higher is better})$$

where \mathcal{E}_i represents the provided explanation for the prediction i . In graph classification, “# of predictions classified into y_i ” corresponds to $|\{G \in \mathbb{G} \mid f(G) = y_i\}|$, where f denotes the model that takes a graph and returns a label. Here, \mathbb{G} presents the graphs in the dataset, including those in training, validation, and test sets. “# of predictions classified into y_i and explained by \mathcal{E}_i ” corresponds to $|\{G \in \mathbb{G} \mid G \in \llbracket \mathcal{E}_i \rrbracket\} \cap \{G \in \mathbb{G} \mid f(G) = y_i\}|$. In PL4XGL, $\llbracket \mathcal{E}_i \rrbracket$ corresponds to $\llbracket P_i \rrbracket$. In SUBGRAPHX, $\llbracket G'_i \rrbracket$ denotes graphs that includes the provided explanation G'_i as a subgraph.

To be meaningful, it is essential to evaluate *Precision* as well to measure how precisely the explanations capture the model’s classifications:

$$Precision = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\# \text{ of predictions classified into } y_i \text{ and explained by } \mathcal{E}_i}{\# \text{ of predictions explained by } \mathcal{E}_i} \quad (\text{higher is better})$$

where “# of predictions explained by \mathcal{E}_i ” corresponds to $|\{G \in \mathbb{G} \mid G \in \llbracket \mathcal{E}_i \rrbracket\}|$.

Figure 1 illustrates how *Generality* and *Precision* are evaluated for a single explanation of PL4XGL (GDL program P_i) and SUBGRAPHX (subgraph G'_i). In the MUTAG dataset, PL4XGL classified the i^{th} test graph into a label y_i and provided the program P_i as an explanation. In the explanation, presents an atom with any type, and presents a carbon. The black colored edges present edges with any types of bonds, and the green colored edges present aromatic bonds (i.e., $\langle [0, 0] \rangle$).

In the MUTAG dataset, PL4XGL classified 124 graphs into y_i , and 96 of the graphs are described by the program P_i . Thus, the generality of the explanation P_i ($Generality_{P_i}$) is 0.77 (96/124), which means 77% of the classifications for the label y_i can be explained by the program P_i . The explanation P_i also precisely captures the classifications of PL4XGL ($Precision_{P_i} = 1.0$ (96/96)); PL4XGL classified all the 96 belonging graphs into the label y_i . The trained GIN classified the test graph into a label, and SUBGRAPHX provided the subgraph G'_i as an explanation. The trained GIN model classified the test graph into a label, and SUBGRAPHX provided G'_i as the explanation. The generality of the subgraph explanation $Generality_{G'_i}$ is 0.38 as the GIN classified 125 graphs into the label, where 48 graphs of them include the subgraph. The subgraph also precisely describes the classifications of the model ($Precision_{G'_i} = 1.0$ (48/48)).

Figure 2 compares the *Generality* and *Precision* of PL4XGL and SUBGRAPHX. In the figures, X-axis and Y-axis presents *Generality* and *Precision*, respectively. Note that the higher is the better (i.e., more

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Fig. 2. Comparison of *Generality* and *Precision* between PL4XGL and SUBGRAPHX. Again, the black squares and the blue lines correspond to PL4XGL and SUBGRAPHX, respectively. In the three webpage datasets (WISCONSIN, TEXAS, and CORNELL), the values of *Generality* and *Precision* of SUBGRAPHX are fixed regardless of the chosen size of the explanations; the blue squares present the *Generality* and *Precision* of SUBGRAPHX.

general and more precise) in both metrics. The black-squares present the performance of PL4XGL, and blue-lines present the performance of SUBGRAPHX. In the three webpage datasets (WISCONSIN, TEXAS, and CORNELL), the explanations of SUBGRAPHX were never generalized, as the subgraphs appear only in the explained classifications, regardless of subgraph size; SUBGRAPHX shows fixed values of *Generality* and *Precision* for the three datasets. This indicates that the subgraph explanations by SUBGRAPHX failed to identify any common patterns across multiple classification results

As depicted in Figure 2, the explanations provided by PL4XGL significantly outperform those from SUBGRAPHX. Except for the BACE dataset, PL4XGL shows a superior balance between *Generality* and *Precision*. In the three webpage datasets (WISCONSIN, TEXAS, and CORNELL), for example, the explanations of PL4XGL are successfully generalized; the program explanations show significantly better *Generality* compared to the subgraph explanations of SUBGRAPHX.

Discussion. Unlike the molecular and synthetic datasets, where nodes are associated with fewer than ten features, nodes in the webpage datasets are linked to specific values of 1,703 features. As there are diverse enough features, no two nodes in these datasets have the same feature values. Note that the subgraph-level explanations need to incorporate the target predicted node as a target explained node of the subgraph (in node classification). As the target node in the subgraph possesses a unique real-valued feature vector, the subgraph explanations are never generalized regardless of

Table 1. *Generality* and *Precision* of PL4XGL for the *citation networks*. The *Generality* and *Precision* of SUBGRAPHX are unavailable (N/A) as it failed to produce explanations within the time budget (i.e., one week).

	<i>Generality</i>			<i>Precision</i>		
	CORA	CITSEER	PUBMED	CORA	CITSEER	PUBMED
PL4XGL	0.11	0.03	0.02	0.95	0.96	0.97
SUBGRAPHX	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

the size of the subgraph explanations. This shows a key limitation of subgraph-level explanations, especially when dealing with high-dimensional feature spaces.

However, the GDL program explanations provided by PL4XGL employ feature value constraints, allowing easier generalization of explanations. In WISCONSIN dataset, for example, PL4XGL provided $364 : [-\infty, 0.5]$, $1046 : [-\infty, 0.5]$ \leftarrow $452 : [0.5, \infty]$ as an explanation. The explanation describes “nodes that 364th and 1046th feature values are equal or less than 0.5 and have a predecessor with the 452th feature value equal or greater than 0.5.” In the dataset, PL4XGL classified 15 nodes into a label, and 13 of them belong to $\llbracket 364 : [-\infty, 0.5], 1046 : [-\infty, 0.5] \leftarrow 452 : [0.5, \infty] \rrbracket$; the generality of the explanation is 0.87 (13/15). Table 1 shows the *Generality* and *Precision* of PL4XGL for the *citation networks*.

E COMPARING TOP-DOWN AND BOTTOM-UP SYNTHESIS ALGORITHMS

We observed that the top-down and bottom-up algorithms have different strengths and weaknesses.

Top-Down Algorithm. The top-down search algorithm has a strength in discovering key feature value intervals. For example, the GDL program $\langle [4, \infty] \rangle \rightarrow \langle [3, 4] \rangle \leftarrow \langle [2, 2] \rangle$ in Table 4 in our paper is learned from the top-down algorithm, and the interval $[3, 4]$ describes key feature values of the label (i.e., middle nodes) that makes the explanation general. Replacing the interval with $[3, 3]$ or $[4, 4]$ significantly reduces its generality. Note that the current bottom-up algorithm is incapable of identifying the key feature value intervals. The bottom-up algorithm produced significantly less effective (low-scored) GDL programs compared to the ones learned from the top-down algorithm in the node classification datasets.

Bottom-Up Algorithm. The bottom-up search algorithm was good at finding key graph structures. For example, the GDL program in Figure 1 is produced from the bottom-up algorithm and is a qualified one. In the MUTAG dataset, there are 125 graphs labeled as 1. The GDL program includes 96 graphs of them, where all the 96 graphs belong to the label. In the program, a majority of the node variables and more than half of the edge variables have the most general constraint (e.g., $\langle \rangle$). This implies that graph structures are important in the MUTAG dataset, and our bottom-up synthesis algorithm successfully discovered such key graph structures. We observed that the top-down search algorithm was less effective at learning such key graph structures, resulting in suboptimal (low-scored) GDL programs.

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